

**MARGINALIZATION WITHIN CASTE: A STUDY OF PREMANAND
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ABSTRACT

The Indian Constitution promises its citizens equality in all aspects. There may be claims of improved condition of the marginalized groups in India. However, the reality tells us a different story. The discrimination at the level of one's race, class, caste, gender, economic status or region has been a major concern in the development of world's largest democracy. As literature is a mirror to the society, many writers have highlighted the issues of socially oppressed class through their works. Premanand Gajvee's Kirwant is one such story that deals with the discriminatory treatment given to a little-known sect of Brahmins who are ill-treated due to their low caste status. The present paper attempts to investigate the issues of marginalization exist within one of the dominant communities in India.

Keywords: Kirwant, Marginality, Oppressive Structure, Minority, Discrimination

Marginality is an experience that affected millions of people all over the world. Certain groups in society denied their basic rights, participation and opportunities on the basis of their class, creed, caste, gender or any other position are considered as marginalized people. They belong to lower, powerless strata who, despite being a large majority, are perceived as less human than others, often viewed with animosity and terror. They are marginalized due to a combination of economic, social, cultural, and political circumstances. Throughout the whole world, most of the marginalized sections of each society have gone through similar kind of oppressive structure. It is also true that the nature and forms of marginalization, oppression and social exclusion have undergone changes over a period of time.

India being a multicultural country, has witnessed substantial numbers of marginalized groups at various levels. Under different economic conditions, the influence of specific historical, cultural, legal and religious factors, marginalization changes in different countries for specific groups. In India, the marginalized groups include Scheduled Tribes who live in close proximity of woods and practice their own rituals, Scheduled Castes, also known as Dalits (the untouchables), a sub-caste in Hindu communities that have historically endured deprivation, discrimination, and social isolation in India due to their perceived 'poor status.' Minorities, a group of people who lived within the society but practiced different religion, beliefs or language and face the slowest development in the socio-economic sectors. Their customs and behaviour, like those of other minorities, are occasionally misunderstood. Women, who cover around fifty percent of the world population, are also marginalized in the terms of gender inequality under various economic conditions and under the influence of

unique historical, cultural, legal, and religious elements. To put it another way, women's exclusion from some jobs opportunities and occupations, incorporated into others, and marginalized in yet others.

Literature, as being considered a mirror up to the society, has been an important tool to represent the prevalent condition of the society. It takes its source from the socio, cultural, economic conditions of the society. Marginalization based on caste, race and gender is one of the major issues in Indian literature. It has been a major source of worry which affected many writers to voice the problems of this deprived section of the society. Badal Sircar, an Indian playwright, in his play 'Stale News' (1983), explores the marginal exploitation and remorseless killings of innocent people with the same anagrams and collages of history and the present with special references of the tribal rebellion more popularly known as Santhal Hool of 1855. Marginalization of the tribal communities has been carrying on from the colonial period down to the present. It was in response to the Santhal Hool that the British colonialists found it essential to corner their community as a separate entity and recognize their territory as Santhal Pargana. Sircar points out the reason for this separate recognition as a precaution taken by the colonizers for any possible threats that could otherwise create stir among the entire Indian mass with such an exemplary event.

Vijay Tendulkar's play 'Kamala' (1981) depicts the psychological and emotional marginalization of women in a domestic milieu through the characters of Sarita and Kamala. Sarita works all day just like a servant taking care of her husband. Still, she has no value or identity in her own home and is marginalized. The tribal woman Kamala is a victim of flesh trade who has to live a life of degradation. Tendulkar portrays the auction of women as to exhibit their predicament in the male dominated society. Through a naturalistic play like Kamala, Vijay Tendulkar brings out the prevailing inequality of gender in the society. Despite that indispensable and multi-dimensional contribution to society, throughout the ages, women are still becoming victims of violence, discrimination and inequality. Marginalization of women has been a recurring theme in the works of Mahasweta Devi. Mahasweta Devi's novel 'Rudali' (1993) portrays the problems of Sanichari, which are the problems of her caste, class and her gender, in the area of low-caste with desperate poverty. Her marginality becomes graver as she is a female and is further dominated by the males of her own caste and community. In the short story 'Draupadi' (1978), Devi depicts the stark picture of a tribal woman whose daily lives are confronted with bodily and psychological struggle, cruelty by the local landlords and poverty in the postcolonial era. It also portrays women as victims of the politics of gender, class and caste played by those different levels of social relationships. Mahesh Dattani's play 'Dance like a Man' (1989), portrays the plight of the dancers who are never privileged for keeping the classical dancing fresh and alive rather the dancers are marginalized. Dancers like Jairaj, Ratna and Lata find politics and patriarchy as the biggest obstacles in their paths to be a dancer. Girish Karnad's play, 'The Fire, and the Rain' (1998) is about the marginalised actors who are hindered by caste, class, and gender. Acting chosen as a profession by Brahmin was not accepted in the medieval period in India. The actors were termed as low-caste. In this play, religion, politics, and patriarchy are the factors responsible for the marginalization of the theatre actors. Through the characters of Visakha and Nittilai, Karnad shows the ever suffering conditions of women at the hands of patriarchal society. Premanand Gajveer is a prominent Marathi playwright. The social commitment reflected through his work reveals the disorganized truth of the society. His writing exposes the unspoken histories of the marginalized people and set right the historical wrongs. His plays

are stark, simple and direct in nature and compel us to reckon with discomfiting realities. Discrimination and exclusion of the certain groups due to their identity based on social, religious, gender, racial and cultural background are common themes of Gajvee's writings. Major among Gajvee's plays are Kirwant, Tan Majori (Arrogance of Body), Ghotbhar Paani (A Sip of Water), Dev Navari (Bride of God), Gandhi and Ambedkar and Jay Jay Raghuvir Samarth. Through these plays, he focuses on the social and political issues which had been rarely discussed.

In this paper, the researcher attempts to explore through Gajvee's play Kirwant how marginalization affects the Brahmins too irrespective of their upper caste status. It also highlights the traditional practices through which the protagonist Siddheshwar, a Chitpawan Bramhin, is oppressed and enforced to follow the religious scriptures. Siddheshwar faces humiliation at the hands of own community. He is oppressed in the name of religion, his rights are compromised and he is ordered to go through atonement for refusing the last/cremation rites of Vedantashastri's mother.

Premanand Gajvee's play 'Kirwant' (2013) portrays the plight of a little-known sect of Chitpawan Bramhins known as Kirwants. Siddheshwarshastri Joshi is a middle-aged Kirwant who resides in the village with his family. He runs his livelihood by performing the last rites at cremations. His younger brother Vasudeo is a smart, unmarried young man of twenty-five years and cadre of Shakha. Siddheshwarshastri has a son Madhu who studies in fourth standard and likes to read Dnyaneshwari. His wife Revati is a house-wife and she wishes to move with her family to some other village where they will be treated well with respect. Though, according to the Hindu scriptures, Siddheshwar performs one of the noblest rituals of human life, he does not get the respect that he deserves.

Despite being a Bramhin, he is ill-treated, just like an untouchable within his own community. His mere existence in auspicious occasions like Satyanaraya Mahapuja is considered a sign of ill omen. Consequently, he is humiliated and ousted from the temple by the people of his own community. His brother, however, Vasudeo doesn't like this work of cremation rites which gives him temporary respect. He goes to Shakha and joins a kind of 'All Hindus are One' movement. Revati wants Vasudeo to marry her younger sister. But, he is unwilling to marry Kirwant's girl. He wants to change his caste by marrying with an upper class Brahmin girl whom he loves too.

The conflict of the story takes place in scene three where Siddheshwar is refused the 'prasad' and unceremoniously is dismissed from the Satyanarayan Mahapuja by Digambarshastri. The non-bramhin people do not find such difference among Brahmins. Once, even a man in the village named Jagtap takes advice from Shiddheshwar to find a match for his daughter.

It's the people from his own community who delineate him and treat him like an outcaste or untouchable. They make him aware that he is Brahmin by birth but by profession, he is as a low-caste and despicable 'Kirwant'. Siddheshwar realizes this when he offers a cup of tea to Dhabushastri who refuses to have it with an excuse of a Sankashti fast and runs away.

Siddheshwar Kindly be seated and have a cup of tea.

Dhabu: Yeah. Oh yes, no objection. (About to sit down, but then rises immediately) Oh dear! I totally forgot. Today happens to be Sankashti, the fast of Lord Ganesh!

Siddheshwar: I get it; you can't drink tea in a kirwant's home.

Dhabu: No, no. Aren't you a human being too? Had I not been on a fast, I could have taken food as well (Kirwant: 44).

Vasudeo becomes angry to hear the humiliation of his brother by Digambarshashtri at Satyanarayan Mahapuja. He becomes rebellious against these customs. He thinks that Siddheshwar should demand an explanation. Here, Vasudeo stands for all the rebels who want to fight against such discrimination. He wants to take revenge with high caste Brahmins by refusing their last rites from Siddheshwar.

However, Siddheshwar is against this fight and considers that his religion regards the priest who performs the last rites as the greatest and holiest of the Brahmins. But when Vedantshastri's mother dies, Vasudeo stops him to attend her last rites.

Dhabu: Siddheshwara, Vedantashastri's mother has breathed her last.

Siddheshwar: Go ahead, I'll follow.

Vasudeo: Go and tell Vedantashastri that Siddheshwar will not come. You did not remember him when he was driven out of the Satyanarayan mahapuja. As long as you are indifferent to his humiliation, Siddheshwar will not come (50).

Dhabushastri is another reputed brahmin, tries to change Siddheshwar's mind, but it is in vain due to Vasudeo's stand. Then, Vedantshastri and Dhabushastri approach Digambarshastri who is leading the Brahmins. They plan to teach a lesson to Vasudeo and Siddheshwarshastri. Gokarnshastri, another Kirwant from another village Sawantwadi, is called for performing the last rites of Vedantshastri's mother. And they excommunicate Siddheshwar's family from the society. Even the grocer refuses to serve food-material to them. Vasudeo is also, bitterly beaten by Ganu and Devrao because he had given the advice that the pig should have touched the pinda of their mother's last rite. In another incident, while Siddheshwar was asking for pity and forgiveness to Digambarshastri, he is kicked and sent out by him.

Digambarshastri cunningly suggests Siddheshwar to kill his own brother Vasudeo. Dhabushastri is a cunning and selfish Brahmin. He advises Siddheshwar that he should perform an atonement ritual and be rid of that mess. Also, he should prepare a gold doll of Vedantshastri's mother and perform the last rites by chanting the appropriate mantras otherwise Vedantshastri's mother would be a witch and torment him and the entire village. Facing these harassments, Siddheshwar becomes anxious.

In another incident, Madhu is given the tea at his friend Tilak's house in a cup that is kept aside which is without a handle. And he is called the son of a carcass-worshipper by his other school-mates as guided by Dhabushastri.

Madhu: The cup had no handle and it burnt my hand. The cup slipped from my hand and tea spilled on my leg.

Madhu: Only my cup was like that. I was about to refuse when Nanu's mother said, 'You are Nanu's friend. Take that cup from the niche over there.' I took the cup and his mother poured tea without touching it (56).

When Vasudeo knows this, he beats Dhabushastri. Consequently, the family of Siddheshwar suffers from frustration, humiliations, harassment. Vasudeo wants to rebel against the system, but Siddheshwarshastri doesn't have the courage to take a stand against the traditions. At last, Siddheshwar dies due to psychological tension in a sudden heart attack. Revati continues his work of cremation rites with giving the lesson of last rite to their son Madhu. She gives him 'Garud- Puran' for recitation. Vasudeo becomes helpless in front of her. Ultimately, just like many other unsuccessful revolts, he too loses his battle against the unjust-system. Kirwant is the play that brings a strange dark world into the light. Most of the plays by Gajvee are related to the subject of 'problem consciousness' of a particularly exploited class from the society. In fact, the classes depicted in his works belonged to lower castes of the system, but in this play, Gajvee deals with the problem of high class brahmins themselves who are far from the creative eyes even.

India is the world's largest democratic nation that one has to be proud of that. But, if one goes deep down into the ground level, one finds that it has been divided into different ideologies, religions, castes and sub-castes. Even the same castes have different beliefs and traditions. From this play, Gajvee presents just an example how the disease of untouchability is deeply rooted in the society. Even the upper caste bramhins haven't escaped from this treatment of humiliation.

However, the larger picture of the canvas, castism within the other castes like Maratha, Mali, Sonar, Shimpi, Lohar, Kumbhar, Mahar, Mang, Mahadev Koli, Koli, Kokna etc., is quite intimidating. One uppercaste detests the other who is inferior. There is discrimination among the untouchables too. Addition to it, a dalit or tribal woman faces discrimination doubly; firstly, by the upper castes, and secondly, by her husband and the patriarchal society. There is still unwillingness of society to break this caste system. No one is ready for 'Roti and Beti exchange' i.e. having food together and having inter-caste marriages which could be an important initiative to break the shackles of caste-system.

It seems to be a strange and startling problem-play which is mainly culture oriented. While studying Gajvee, it is found that he has deeply analyzed the cultural problems and exposed the causes of injustice along with a smooth style of dramatic technique in his plays.

REFERENCES

1. American Journal of Sociology (May, 1928): 881-893.
2. Gajvee, Premanand. The Strength of Our Wrists. New Delhi: Narayana Publication, 2013.
3. "Intersectionality of Marginalization and Inequality: A Case Study of Muslims in India ." Journal of Political Sciences & Public Affairs 04(01) DOI:10.4172 (January 2016): 2332- 0761.
4. Mohan, Mirajkar Arjun. "The Select Plays of Wilson August and Premanand Gajvi A Culture Study, PhD Dissertation." <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/223216> (2015). Dept of English.